

NOTES

Manganese(II) Complexes of *N*-Phenyl-*N'*-(6-substituted)benzothiazolythiocarbamide

A. D. NAKRANI, B. V. RATHOD and K. J. SHAH*

University Department of Chemistry,
Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364-002

Manuscript received 27 May 1991, accepted 3 September 1991

SEVERAL complexes of thiocarbamides¹ have been reported, but nothing has appeared about the manganese(II) complexes of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-substituted)benzothiazolythiocarbamides. We describe herein the synthesis of such complexes and their characterisation by spectral, magnetic, conductance and elemental analyses.

Experimental

All reagents were of A.R. grade and were used as such.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Backmann DU-7 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility in the solid state was measured at room temperature by the Gouy technique. Elemental analyses were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

N-Phenyl-*N'*-(6-substituted)benzothiazolythiocarbamides were prepared by the condensation of 2-amino-(6-substituted)benzothiazoles² with *p*-substituted-arylisothiocyanates⁴. A mixture of 2-amino-(6-substituted)benzothiazole (0.4 mol) in dry benzene (80 ml) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.4 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h and then cooled. Benzene was removed by distillation and the resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether and dilute HCl and recrystallised from dioxane.

Preparation of Mn^{II} complexes: An aqueous solution of the manganese acetate (0.05 mol) and solution of the ligand (0.1 mol) in DMF were mixed in the presence of the acetate buffer (pH=6.5) and the mixture was digested on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solids were washed with water and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes decomposed at ~195–210°.

Results and Discussion

The complexes decomposed at 195–210°. The low electrical conductivity (10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Ir spectra of the ligand showed three bands at 1 395–1 595, 1 160–1 420 and 940–1 140 cm⁻¹ due to mixed vibrations of thioamide group⁵. Other bands were observed at 3 150 (NH), 1 635 (C=N cyclic) and 750 cm⁻¹ (C=S). In the ir spectra of the complexes, thioamide bands blue-shifted appreciably indicating M–S linkage (320–340 cm⁻¹) in the complexes. The lowering in ν C=N (cyclic) frequencies in the complexes (1 540–1 610 cm⁻¹) showed coordination from the nitrogen atom to the metal⁶. Moreover, a broad band was observed around 3 400 cm⁻¹(OH) in the spectra of the complexes, which was absent in the spectra of the ligands. This band indicates the presence of coordinated water molecule in the complexes. A new band observed at ~520 cm⁻¹ proved M–N linkage in the complexes. The complexes showed other ir bands at 3 180–3 230 (NH) and 2 900–2 925 (C–H); complexes of sl. nos. 3 and 6 showed νC–Cl band at 725 and 720 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The ground term of the manganese ion is sextet^{6g}. The ground term in octahedral stereochemistry is

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
		Mn	C	H	N	S	Cl
1.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.75 (7.77)	52.36 (52.25)	4.15 (4.35)	11.95 (12.19)	18.40 (18.58)	—
2.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.49 (7.82)	50.01 (49.93)	4.20 (4.16)	11.60 (11.65)	17.84 (17.75)	—
3.	Mn(C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.38 (7.53)	46.00 (46.04)	3.35 (3.29)	11.45 (11.51)	17.50 (17.54)	9.70 (9.71)
4.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.75 (7.66)	53.45 (53.56)	4.62 (4.74)	11.75 (11.72)	17.90 (17.85)	—
5.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.43 (7.34)	51.25 (51.27)	4.45 (4.54)	11.25 (11.22)	17.10 (17.09)	—
6.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.12 (7.25)	47.65 (47.50)	3.65 (3.69)	11.00 (11.08)	16.85 (16.89)	9.34 (9.36)

*Corresponding ligand: C₁₆H₁₃N₂S₂=*N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolythiocarbamide; C₁₆H₁₃N₂OS₂=*N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-methoxy)benzothiazolythiocarbamide; C₁₄H₁₀N₂S₂Cl=*N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-chloro)benzothiazolythiocarbamide; C₁₆H₁₃N₂S₂=*N*-(*p*-tolyl)-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolythiocarbamide; C₁₆H₁₃N₂OS₂=*N*-(*p*-tolyl)-*N'*-(6-methoxy)benzothiazolythiocarbamide; C₁₆H₁₃N₂S₂Cl=*N*-(*p*-tolyl)-*N'*-(6-chloro)benzothiazolythiocarbamide.

${}^6A_{1g}$. There can be no spin-allowed transitions. The transition of the spectrum is assigned from ${}^6A_{1g}$ ground term to quartet excited terms. The lowest quartet term is ${}^4T_{1g}(G)$ followed by ${}^4T_{2g}$. The two bands observed at $\sim 18\,500$ and $\sim 22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ respectively, suggest an octahedral geometry⁷.

Magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} complexes (5.80 – 6.1 B.M.) indicate that Mn^{II} ion has five unpaired electrons with ${}^6A_{1g}$ ground state. It is orbitally singlet term giving no orbital contribution to magnetic moment. It has also no TIP effect and no reduction in magnetic moment due to coupling with higher ligand field terms. The magnetic moment values are close to 5.92 B.M. Hence the probable structure of the complexes is distorted octahedral with M–N and M–S binding sites.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of Bhavnagar University for facilities and to Prof. M. M. Taqui Khan, Director, C.S.M.C.R.I., Bhavnagar for the spectral and magnetic data.

References

1. B. K. MOHAPATRA and D. R. RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 284; M. M. KHAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1395; F. A. COTTON, O. D. FANT and J. T. MOGUE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 17; N. K. AGARWAL and K. P. SHRIVASTVA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1040.
2. P. BHARGAVA and S. SHARMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **48**, 905.
3. C. G. STUCKWISCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3417.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry including Qualitative Organic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1978.
5. E. SPINNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1237.
6. D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2725.
7. N. S. GILL, R. S. NYHOLM, G. A. BARCLAY, T. I. CHRISTIE and P. J. PAULING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 88.